

HUMAN INTUITION WHEN DESIGNING FOR EMOTIONS: HOW THE DESIGNER'S PERSONAL BACKGROUND CAN HELP (OR RUIN) A PROJECT

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ABSTRACT

Emotional design usually refers to designing in order to evoke or prevent particular emotions among users. This workshop is not aimed at discussing solely users' emotions, it is also focused on understanding how the designer's emotional experience might influence his/her work. Emotion and reasoning are not antonyms. Emotion can even help us to make better decisions, e.g., working as an adaptive sign of danger, when basic survival needs are threatened. In the tradition of cognitive research on decision-making, emotions can play an informational role, filling in the lack of information that people sometimes find when they need to make decisions. It is a heuristic mechanism, which is understood, in the cognitive sciences, as intuitive, since intuition is strongly based on emotion. Professionals in a variety of fields, such as design, medicine and law, might need to evaluate diverse situations and make quick decisions, grounded on impressions built in a few seconds of observation. These impressions have an emotional basis and are commonly based on personal and professional previous experiences, which are part of the mentioned heuristic process. The lack of information that would allow designers to logically analyse the problem is filled in with affective content. This way, the workshop goal is to facilitate designers to understand how their intuitive thinking can help (or ruin) their design.

KEYWORDS: *design for emotions; intuition; rationality; design process*

INTRODUCTION: BACKGROUND ISSUES

Emotional design usually refers to designing in order to evoke or prevent particular emotions. Desmet (2009) described four approaches to design for emotions: (a) the user-based approach has the users' emotions as foundations of the design and usually includes them in the design process; (b) in the designer-based perspective, professionals aim at challenging users with innovative artefacts; (c) using the theory-based approach, professionals search insights in theory to feed the process, while (d) the research-based perspective is grounded on user research.

When designers are not based on user research, they might be led to ignore that their experience does not necessarily represent that of the target group, since emotional experience is commonly understood as triggered by stimuli that might change among distinct types of user/person (Frijda, 1986). This means that the same stimulus, such as the sound of rain, can

trigger relaxation among those who enjoy water, or even fear, e.g., if it is heard by a community that has been through some kind of natural disaster related to water. Thus, it is possible that designers, trusting on their views on how to trigger a certain emotion, could design biased solutions to simple problems.

This workshop is not aimed at discussing solely users' emotions, but it is also focused on understanding how the designer's emotional experience might influence their work. Emotion and reasoning are not antonyms. Emotion can even help us to make better decisions, e.g., working as an adaptive sign of danger, when basic survival needs are threatened. In the tradition of cognitive research on decision-making (Tversky and Kahneman, 1974), Kahneman (2003) states that emotions can play an informational role, filling in the lack of information that people sometimes find when they need to make decisions. It is a heuristic mechanism, which is understood, in the cognitive sciences, as intuitive, since intuition is strongly based on emotion. Professionals in a variety of fields, such as design,

medicine and law, might need to evaluate diverse situations and make quick decisions, grounded on impressions built in a few seconds of observation. These impressions have an emotional basis and are commonly based on personal and professional previous experiences, which are part of the mentioned heuristic process. The lack of information that would allow designers to logically analyse the problem is filled in with affective content.

One of the most common theoretical perspectives in the Design and Emotion field is the Appraisal Theory. It matches perfectly Kahneman and Tversky's (1974, reviewed by Kahneman, 2003) perspective on intuition, since they are both originated in cognitive psychology. In the Appraisal Theory, emotions are understood as the result of a user's appraisal of products, services or any other stimulus (Frijda, 1986; Demir, Desmet, Hekkert, 2009). How does this product relate to my well being? If the answer reveals expected or real benefits, a positive emotion is likely to occur (e.g., joy, happiness). If it is negative, a negative emotion might be the outcome (e.g., sadness).

Also, users' concerns might influence the emotional outcomes of people's interaction with products and services. Concerns are a person's goals, motives, or any other sensitivity (Frijda, 1986), such as being safe or have healthy food on a daily basis. By understanding users concerns and how consumers appraise products and services, it is possible to understand what triggers these emotions, and to evoke them through design. It states a connection between causes (design elements) and effects (emotional impact of design).

The mentioned guidelines refer to a variety of possibilities. They range from very concrete information to abstract properties of a product. As examples, it is possible to mention the use of marble in home projects (concrete information), if it is a trigger for sophistication to a specific type of user (in projects that aim at evoking this experience), and to design of a device to help older people to achieve everyday goals (abstract), instead of solving the problem for them (if "do it yourself" is a common trigger to pride in this target group), in a project to stimulate pride among the elder. These examples reinforce the idea that emotion has an individual basis and that distinct kinds of users might appraise similar situations in very distinct ways, which means that what triggers the same emotions might change from one target group to another.

Thus, being intuitive can be particularly dangerous to beginners and/or professionals with a lack of knowledge about the target group, since intuition will work based on the information and impressions they already have. On the other hand, knowing how intuition works can be a great tool, when used consciously. It allows us to be creative without overestimating our knowledge about the target group. This way, intuition is best employed when practiced.

WORKSHOP GOAL AND APPROACH

The workshop goal is to facilitate designers to understand how their intuitive thinking can help (or ruin) their design. Through

an exercise described below, they will be trained to understand how their intuition works, facilitating self-knowledge, and their intuitive solutions will be confronted with user research. In order to achieve this goal, the workshop will have five moments:

- a) Short design task (75 min): A design task will be based on Demir, Ozkaramanli and Desmet (2010) experiences. Emotion formulas will be built by the design team, including the definition of a product to be designed for a low-income Brazilian group¹, as well as a discussion about the emotion (pride) to be stimulated among them. After that, a concern analysis will be developed, followed by the formulation of design concepts and their presentation to the group.
- b) Projection of a film about the target group (10 min): A short documentary on pride, filmed in this low-income Brazilian community, will be shown to the design team. It shows people's testimonial on events that made them proud of something or somebody.
- c) Mini lecture on Intuition (20 min): The lecture will be given by the workshop facilitator (and author of this proposal), and will cover the main topic "How (design) intuition works", following the model described in the introduction.
- d) Analysis on how the design team would change (or not) their design after watching the film (45 min): Participants will be asked to evaluate the actual potential of their design to evoke the intended emotion (pride) and, if needed, adjust and/or criticise their design.
- e) Facilitator's analysis on the design team's intuitive thinking (30 min): In order to stimulate self-knowledge, the workshop facilitator will finish the activities by analysing participants' design decisions, showing how intuition affected their design in good and/or bad directions, which means, helping to achieve the design aim or doing the opposite.

INTENDED NUMBER OF ATTENDEES

Maximum: 30; Minimum: 12

DURATION OF THE WORKSHOP

Half-day (3 hours)

THE PREFERRED CITY FOR THE WORKSHOP

Bogotá

1 The group of freelance cleaners was defined to set a target with characteristics potentially distinct from the design team.

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SPACE/ROOM NEEDED TO CONDUCT THE WORKSHOP

Chairs and table to develop work in groups.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Conselho Nacional de Desenvolvimento Científico e Tecnológico (CNPq)

REFERENCES

DEMIR, E.; DESMET, P. M. A.; HEKKERT, P. (2009) *Appraisal Patterns of Emotions in Human-Product Interaction*. International Journal of Design. vol.3, n.2.

DEMIR, E.; OZKARAMANLI, D.; DESMET, P.M.A. (2010). How to Design for Emotions: Experiences in a Course. In: K. SATO, P.M.A. DESMET; P. HEKKERT; G. LUDDEN; A. MATHEW (eds.), *Proceedings of the 7th International Design & Emotion Conference 2010*, Chicago (IL, USA), 2010.

DESMET, P. (2009). Special Issue Editorial: Design & Emotion. International Journal of Design 3(2), 1-6.

FRIJDA, N.H. (1986). *The Emotions*. Cambridge, Cambridge University Press.

KAHNEMAN, D. (2003). A Perspective on Judgment and Choice: Mapping Bounded Rationality. *American Psychologist* 58(9), 697-720.

MARGOLIN, V. (1997). Getting to know the user. *Design Studies* 18(3), 227-236.

TVERSKY, A., & KAHNEMAN, D. (1974). Judgment under Uncertainty: Heuristics and Biases. *Science* 185 (4157), 1124-1110.